

Expanding HCXAI in the Age of AI Agents: Challenges and Recommendations

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AI agents—autonomous, multi-tasking systems beyond traditional AI—will reshape human-AI interaction shifting the focus from a simple human-versus-system autonomy debate to a triadic model: human users, AI agents, and digital resources. Further, the widespread adoption of agentic systems as consumer products will accelerate the large-scale integration of novel human-AI agent hybridization into everyday life, necessitating renewed examinations of agent identity, accountability, and trust in AI agent-rich digital environments. In this position paper, we argue that Human-Centered eXplainable AI (HCXAI) can help addressing these trends by developing causal explanations that span multiple levels of abstraction and integrate different digital resources, as well as personalized, interactive explanations that serve as identity warranty mechanisms when humans and AI agents interact together and with other digital resources. Finally, as a research field, HCXAI can help redesign the explainability-trust relation in these novel digital ecosystems. We introduce examples of these explanations, calling for an interdisciplinary collaboration to refine these high-level proposals and ensure a still human-centered digital future.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Applied computing**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; **Philosophical/theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence**;

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Introduction

The Human-Centered eXplainable AI (HCXAI) paradigm posits that XAI is more than just ‘opening’ the AI black-box: it requires understanding who opens it, what they are trying to achieve, and design explanations that meet these needs [3, 4]. In this position paper, we suggest that recent HCXAI efforts to address the explainability of Large Language Models (LLMs)¹ should be realigned with the rapid evolution of AI agents—autonomous, multi-tasking systems that act on digital environments. To do so, HCXAI must expand its focus from explainability as a means of interpreting model outputs to explainability as a mechanism for managing accountability in action. Human-centered explanations must clarify agency with causality, provide warrants of online identity, and foster trust across human-AI agent-digital resource interactions. This is our take on “operationalizing human-centered perspectives in XAI” [4, pag. 2] in the age of AI agents. We elaborate on this argument identifying three HCXAI challenges related to AI agent explainability and proposing recommendations to ensure that explainability evolves with the rise of agentic AI.

Beware the dawn of the AI agent age

What are AI agents? In the domain of generative AI, the term **AI agent** refers to systems powered by LLMs that can execute a wide range of tasks while manifesting agentic capabilities [11, 18].² Here, **agency** denotes the capacity to make decisions, act, and influence the behavior of other systems in a working environment through a combination of programming instructions and learning capabilities. It emerges from a combination of interactivity, autonomy, and adaptability [8, 9].³ Unlike traditional machine learning-based AI systems designed for specific tasks, such as image

¹See, for instance, the ACM 2025 HCXAI workshop proposal at <https://drive.google.com/file/d/182UnoNxuzr0T0ztB9suKnhhNw8YmYbVn/view>

²We prefer the term **AI agent** over **AI assistant** [12], as the latter implies social roles that may be philosophically problematic [7, 10].

³We note that agency does not require possessing mental states, such as those humans have [8, 9].

classification or risk assessment, AI agents leverage natural language interfaces to interpret prompts, and execute actions via integrated tools, accessing external APIs, search engines, and plugins, while self-improving based on user feedback and inter-agent communication. Importantly, while AI systems, including LLMs, typically *suggest*, AI agents *do*. In this sense, they are akin to new generation, multi-task and multi-system instances of Robotic Process Automation [14]. By interacting with their environment and acting upon internal logic, they embody a genuine form of artificial agency that has long been a central focus of AI research [20].

AI agents: reality of fiction? AI agents are designed to automate routine tasks such as scheduling meetings, finalizing hotel reservations, as well as managing conversations on behalf of human users. Although these systems remain largely aspirational at present, a few development frameworks have already emerged, each offering unique capabilities to enhance automation and user interaction. For instance, OpenAI’s Operator⁴ is engineered to autonomously execute web-based tasks by interacting with graphical elements on webpages via a ‘universal interface for AI.’ Microsoft’s AutoGen⁵ provides an open-source framework for building AI agents that cooperate to solve tasks, focusing on multi-agent orchestration and autonomous workflows within digital ecosystems. Google DeepMind’s Gemini 2.0 Flash Thinking⁶ leverages multimodal reasoning and native tool use—such as integrated search and code execution—to address complex queries. Fully autonomous AI agents remain aspirational, but the recent DeepSeek case highlights that the race toward agentic AI is well underway. In the near term, they may assist only with routine tasks. However, future AI agents could manage job applications, financial planning, and even social interactions.

Human-AI interaction research with AI agents

The rise of agentic AI will reshape human-AI interaction research. Below, we highlight two trends that require attention.

First, while humans directly engage with digital resources—such as webpages, apps, intranet portals, online forums, databases and various AI systems, soon these interactions will be increasingly mediated by personalized AI agents acting on their behalf [12]. This evolution gives rise to a **triadic relation among the human user, their AI agent(s), and the digital resources accessed by them**, including other AI agents or more ‘traditional’ AI systems. In this new paradigm, autonomy is shared: each component possesses a distinct degree of autonomy, expressed in relation to the specific tasks they perform [16, 23]. As a result, it becomes essential to design (1) human-centered interfaces for interacting directly with AI agents, and (2) AI agent-centered mechanisms for them to engage with digital resources. Notably, through interaction, AI agents will reshape digital resources and be reshaped in the process. As a result, while these agents learn and evolve by managing and processing information on behalf of humans, challenges inherent to traditional AI systems, such as lack of transparency, risk of discrimination, and vulnerability to adversarial perturbations, will propagate throughout the triadic relation, requiring the development of novel approaches to manage risk, ensure accountability, and foster trust.

Second, it is reasonable to expect that AI agents will soon be offered as services by major players in the generative AI space, as well as by competitive open-source frameworks. Consumers will simply choose their preferred service provider, select a fee plan, and manage the operations of their personal ‘herd’ of AI agents. Consequently, from a human-AI interaction perspective, **consumer and their personalized AI agents will constitute hybrid agentic systems**, that is, systems emerging from interactions between human users and AI agent enhancing their cognitive, epistemic, and, crucially, agentic capabilities through multimodal and multi-system interactivity. (Traditional AI systems, such

⁴<https://openai.com/index/introducing-operator/>

⁵<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/autogen/>

⁶<https://deepmind.google/technologies/gemini/flash/>

as a medical diagnostics or pricing tools, are typically designed to augment cognitive and epistemic capabilities of their users by sharing predictions, but not agentic abilities.) Then, as AI agents will become increasingly integrated into various sectors of society, these human agent-AI agent (hybrid) systems will shape digital ecosystems at scale, while communicating and interacting with each other, much like shepherds and their cattle transform the natural landscape with pastoralism.⁷ This large-scale agentic hybridization calls for a reexamination of notions of agent identity, accountability, and trust in the context of AI agent-rich environments. Moving away from Heidegger’s ideal of ‘humanity as shepherd of Being,’⁸ the rise of AI agent will give us the more pragmatic role of ‘shepherds of our agentic machines.’⁹

In summary, the rise of AI agents compels us to reexamine our approach to human-AI interactions starting with the human-centered AI paradigm, which has traditionally focused itself on the binary relation between human control over (AI) system automation [24]. Approaches such as complementarity, distributed cognition, and ‘AI extenders’ offer valuable insights to human-AI agent hybridization [6, 13, 19]. However, it is **the HCXAI framework that can help addressing the rise of AI agents** by providing appropriate explanations for their activities, ensuring accountability across multi-layered and multi-system interactions, and maintaining trust in settings where the interaction between humans and digital resources, e.g., medical AI systems or investment platforms, are mediated by AI agents. To do so, HCXAI has to redirect efforts from interpreting AI system outcomes to explaining actions of agentic AI while keeping the ‘human’ at the center. The following section outlines three challenges and simple recommendations to adapt HCXAI methods to AI agent-rich environment.

HCXAI research in the age of AI agents: Three challenges and recommendations

I. AI agent activity requires causal and deep explanations

AI agents magnify classical HCXAI challenges, such as the lack of transparency in decision-making and the need to align AI system processes with human values. These systems may optimize unintended objectives, leading to unpredictable or even harmful outcomes. Data used to train them—especially the LLMs underpinning their logical capabilities—remain largely inaccessible, with minimal oversight on how biases propagate through the training pipeline and beyond. As AI agents are designed to autonomously act upon information, this can amplify inequalities and propagate errors manifold, especially when humans and multiple AI agents operate together committing fraud, spreading misinformation, or violating regulations. As a result, it can become difficult to pinpoint responsibility in such hybrid systems: their law-breaking actions may involve accidental combinations of computational errors, random effects, perturbations, or user-instructed fraudulent behavior.

Thus, **explanations for AI agent activities—and those of the human-AI agent hybrid—must be both causal and deep.** By *causal*, we mean that explanations should uncover the underlying decision-making processes that lead to a given agentic action: agency enables interventions on the environment and interventions are at the core of causality.¹⁰ HCXAI research can start integrating methods from causal inference and structural causal models, and counterfactual reasoning [17]. This emphasis on causality may seemingly contrast with traditional AI systems, where explanations

⁷Hybridization happens in human-AI interactions as well [6, 13, 19]. However, traditional AI systems does not have agentic capabilities.

⁸In his *Letter on Humanism*, 1947, Heidegger famously claimed that humanity is not the lord of the beings, but, rather the shepherd of Being (“Der Mensch ist nicht der Herr des Seienden. Der Mensch ist der Hirt des Seins.”) Namely, humanity does not control or dominate Being (*Sein*) but rather cares for and listens to it, allowing it to unfold, like a shepherd attends their cattle with care.

⁹A reality that materializes Günther Anders’—a student of Heidegger—pessimistic perspective on our humanity in the age of technology: “[...] we are certainly not ‘shepherds of [B]eing.’ Far rather we might consider ourselves the ‘shepherds of our product- and gadget-world’ as a world that needs us, more strikingly than we do ourselves, as servants (e.g., as consumers or possessors)” [1, pag. 281]. This perspective is challenged by the prospect of artificial general intelligence, where AI agents may no longer require human oversight or ‘shepherds’ to guide their actions.

¹⁰Improving on current frameworks for LLM reasoning traces, such as ReAct [28].

often (but not exclusively) describe statistical correlations in relation to the outcome. However, correlative explanations are still necessary in the context of the relation human user-AI agent-digital resources. In fact, at selected steps of the activity causal chain, we may provide information on the outputs of an AI system that are used by the AI agent to act on the environment. Simply put, human-AI agent-digital resource interactions require substantially augmenting the type of explanations we consider in HCXAI including causality to address agency systematically. (Literature on causality, machine learning and their issues provides a solid starting point [5, 22, 27].) That is why *deep* explanations require reconstructing the full causal chain of an AI agent’s activity, which involves considering (1) appropriate user-dependent explanatory levels, and (2) relevant sub-relations with humans and other systems—i.e., the *who* and *what* of HCXAI in AI agent-rich interactions. For instance, user-dependent explanatory levels may refer *strategic level*, where explanations convey the overall objective guiding the agent, such as minimizing risk in automated trading. The *tactical level* specifies the intermediate decision processes, such as forecasting models that indicate probabilities or trends instead. Finally, the *operational level* focuses on the precise execution details, such as the triggering of stop-loss orders or other specific control measures. Different users access different levels and all explanations describe explicitly the digital resources interacting with the AI agent and any human intervention, supporting audit trails of human-AI agent-AI interactions at scale.

An example is in order. **Human-centered explanations will be key for the improvement of personalized AI agents through user feedback.**¹¹ This will become particularly relevant in consumer-based services, where users must understand whether, how, and when to intervene in their AI agent’s decision-making as part of their ongoing interaction with the system (Much like shepherds tending to their cattle, following our bucolic analogy.) Causal and deep human-centered explanations would then (1) identify and elaborate on stopping events in AI agent activity, such as endless feedback loops, sudden drops in performance, or rule-based triggers (e.g., halting a financial transaction that exceeds a certain risk threshold predicted by another AI system) at different levels, and (2) provide recommendations tailored to the user’s expectations, available resources, and risk appetite. Designing appropriate interfaces will not be an easy task, however. For instance, the frequency of explanation and user feedback would depend on various factors, including the type of AI agent and its operating environment (e.g., automatically creating music vs. triggering pharmacological treatments in a hospital.)

II. Fighting fire with fire: Safeguarding online identity with agentic explanations

The deployment of AI agents introduces new risks in online identity management, necessitating the integration of novel explanation-aware verification capabilities. The challenge for HCXAI lies in promoting explanations as identity verification structures of hybrid human-AI agent systems. These explanations must clearly report on human-initiated actions vs. AI-agent-driven activities, providing a transparent and time-sensitive view of agency distribution within hybrid systems, both for its human users and third parties. Simply embedding in explanations traditional methods, such as CAPTCHA gatekeeping, is unlikely to suffice in a future where human-versus-AI agent recognition systems may necessitate invasive detection techniques, such as behavioral or biometric measures, that raise their own ethical concerns. Here, HCXAI research can intervene by developing explanation-aware identity mechanisms that transparently communicate who—or what—is acting in digital environments. Unlike binary systems like CAPTCHA, real-time, interactive explanations would empower users to understand, modify, or halt a hybrid system’s activities dynamically.

¹¹For instance, even now, systems like ChatGPT solicit user feedback to refine responses. This is an OpenAI-triggered process, however.

But how? Again, an example is due. For instance, designers could consider providing consumer subscribing to their agentic AI service with a **master AI agent** serving as a warranty of online identity, overseeing the actions of other AI agents linked to that user and ensuring that their digital presence remains verifiable. Unlike standard AI agents, master AI agents would operate under stricter requirements, such as cryptographic signatures of their activities, ensuring that every interaction with them can be traced and justified. (After all, every shepherd needs a good cattle dog.) These agents would offer real-time, interactive explanations that clarify the origin and intent of AI-mediated actions, the degree of AI autonomy versus human involvement, and historical accountability through an auditable explanation trail via natural language interfaces. Or, as part of post-hoc evaluation of completed activities, for instance, in professional or social platforms, when a user engages in discussions via AI-assisted communication tools, these master AI agents could generate explanations indicating which parts of the conversation were AI-assisted (either deterministically or probabilistically with ‘artificial agency scores’), ensuring clarity in human-human interactions. In identity-sensitive environments such as digital contracts or content authorship, their use of cryptographically signed logs could further ensuring transparency and control over the identity of human users, AI agents, and other digital resources.

III. Rethinking explainability and trust in human-AI agent-AI interactions

As AI agents will become prominent in digital ecosystems, our understanding of trust and its relation with explainability must be reconceptualized. In fact, trust and explainability will extend to different interactions, including AI agent-AI agent and AI agent-digital resource ones, which traditional trust models—rooted in human cognitive and affective frameworks—and explainability methods struggle to address. Here, HCXAI remains relevant as the goal—despite the prominence of interactions between different systems—is to ensure that AI agent autonomy remains explainable and gives human users reasons to trust these systems. **As a field, HCXAI will provide sought-after methodological guidance**, promoting studies that investigate the effects of casual and deep explanations on (different types of) human users, and the provision of information to them *and* their AI agents to ensure the agent type-dependent trustworthiness of the systems they interact with. Some good news: computer science literature abounds of multi-agent trust(worthiness) and reputation measures based on, for instance, reliability, data integrity levels, and secure communication protocols [21]. Additionally, quantitative models of ‘trust as anti-monitoring’ offer a mental state-independent perspective on trusting in interactions between different systems, including AI agents [15, 25, 26]. Altogether, this program can leverage a precise formalization of trust in AI agent-rich environment and a formalization of its relation with explainability helping advance empirical research on trust in AI and overcoming methodological fragmentation and other long-standing challenges in that field [2].

Conclusions

The integration of AI agents into our digital ecosystem challenges traditional human-centered frameworks, necessitating to consider the perspective of human users, their AI agents, and the digital resources interacting with them. HCXAI can help managing this new perspective implementing causality-aware explanation layers, developing explanation-based identity warranty mechanisms, and helping redesign the explainability-trust relation in AI agent-rich ecosystems. We call for interdisciplinary collaboration to refine these high-level proposals and ensure a still human-centered digital future for our societies, including those who, due to socio-economic barriers, risk being left behind in the AI agent race.

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